

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

ASSESSMENT OF SELF-MEDICATION PRACTICE AND DRUG STORAGE IN DUBER TOWN, OROMIA UNIQUE ZONE, OROMIA REGION, CENTRAL ETHIOPIA

Sintayehu Alemu, Andualem Tesfaye*

School of Pharmacy, Faculty of Health Sciences, Jimma University, Jimma, Ethiopia.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 19/05/2018

Available online
05/06/2018

Keywords

Self-Medication,
Drug-Storage,
Illnesses,
Duber Town.

ABSTRACT

A number of individuals in developing countries do not seek health service for their illnesses; instead they commonly use self-medication. Self-medication could be using drugs existing in home like over the counter drugs, traditional medicine, prescription only drug. Inappropriate storage and use of medicines at home could have a direct influence on public health, the environment and the health-care services and it increases the risk of self-medication. A community based cross-sectional study was conducted in Duber Town from February 9/2016-20/2016. Data was collected by semi structure-questionnaire consisting questions on general demographic, socio-economic as well as on perceived illness/ symptoms in the past one month and actions taken for it. The data collected was screened before it is analyzed. A total 333 respondents interviewed, 120 (36%) had reported different symptoms of illness. 45 (37.5%) of the respondents reported with illness practiced self-medication. The most frequently class of drugs for self-medication were analgesics/antipyretics and antimicrobial which account 24(38.1%) each followed by anti-helminthes 6(9.5%). 57(17.1%) reported drug storing practice in the house. The most commonly stored drugs are analgesics/antipyretics (48.5%) followed by antimicrobial (45.5%). There is high prevalence of self-medication practiced and Analgesic/antipyretics, antibiotics and anti-helminthes were identified commonly used drugs for self-medication. Moreover Community practiced drugs storage in the house and it is important to provide health education on risk and benefit of self-medication and drug storage.

Corresponding author

Andualem Tesfaye Sebsibe

B. Pharm, MSc.

Lecturer, School of Pharmacy

Faculty of Medical Sciences, Jimma University,

Ethiopia, P.O.Box: 378

+251911954865

andextes@gmail.com; andualem.tesfaye@ju.edu.et

Please cite this article in press as **Sintayehu Alemu et al.** Assessment of Self-Medication Practice and Drug Storage in Duber Town, Oromia Unique Zone, Oromia Region, Central Ethiopia. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018;8(05).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Self-medication (SM) is use of drugs to treat self-diagnosed disorders or symptoms, or the intermittent or continued use of a prescribed drug for chronic or recurrent disease or symptoms. In practice, it also includes use of the medication of family members, especially where the treatment of children or the elderly is concerned. It involves the use of medicinal products by the consumer to treat self-recognized disorders or symptoms, or the intermittent or continued use of a medication prescribed by a physician for chronic or recurring disease or symptoms [1,2].

There is a lot of public and professional concern about the irrational use of drugs. In developing countries like India, easy availability of a wide range of drugs coupled with inadequate health services result in increased proportions of drugs used as SM compared to prescribed drugs [3]. Hazards of self-medication may also include: drug interaction, drug dependence, addiction and overdosing [4]. The use of prescription only medications without the knowledge of physicians can be less beneficial or even be dangerous for the patient [5].

Although, over the counter (OTC) drugs are meant for self-medication and are of proved efficacy and safety, their improper use due to lack of knowledge of their side effects and interactions could have serious complications, especially in extremes of ages (children and old age) and special physiological conditions like pregnancy and lactation [6]. Minimize the risk of non-prescription drugs Food and Drug Authority (FDA) has strongly advocated that labeling of the OTC drugs should be easy to understand by the consumer and should contain the list of active ingredients, warnings, directions and inactive ingredients [7].

Storing medicines at home might increase the risk of self-medication, and some authors have reported a high frequency of exchange of self-medication between families (members). Inappropriate storage and use of medicines at home could have a direct influence on public health, the environment and the health-care services and it increases the risk of self-medication [8].

Due to lack of proper health education to the population, the practice of SM and improper drug storage is becoming one of the public health problems [1]. The rising level of resistance of infectious agents on the drug effect can be related to SM as one main factor and Poor drug storage is one of the reasons that can decrease the effectiveness of the drug.

There has not yet been any research conducted on self-medication and drug storage in Duber Town. Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess self-medication practice and drug storage in Duber Town Community, Oromia Unique Zone, and Oromia Region, Central Ethiopia.

METHODS

Study Area

The Study was conducted in Duber Town, Oromia Unique Zone, and Oromia Region, Central Ethiopia. Duber town is located at 68km to North of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The total population of the town was 5410(2580 males, 2830 females) in 1420 households. There are one health center and one private clinic in the town.

Study design and population

A cross-sectional study was conducted using semi structured questioner consisting of general socio-demographic, socio-economic, perceived illness and action taken to overcome the illness and practice of drug storage among Duber town community. A sample 333 was determined by using single population proportion formula by considering 50% estimated proportion of self-medication among Duber town community because there is no such study conducted in the study area. Systematic random sampling technique was used to select the households.

Data collection and management

Semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information. The respondents were interviewed in local language, Afan Oromo. The data was collected by trained data collector. To assure the quality of the data, questionnaire was pre-tested before the actual data collection. Every day, the collected data was reviewed. The collected data was checked for completeness of information and then it was analyzed manually and presented in the form of frequency table, graphs & charts.

Ethical Consideration

An official letter was written from Jimma University College Health Science, Department of Pharmacy to a Duber Town Administrative Office to get permeation for data collection. Verbal consent was obtained from the respondent for their willingness to participate on the study. The respondents were informed about the objective of the study and confidentiality of the information before the interview.

RESULTS

This study canvassed population of 333. The socio-demographic and economic background of the respondents showed that, 183 (40.6%) were males and 150 (59.4%) were females. 130(39%) of the respondents were illiterate, 91 (27.3%) were attended primary school, 78 (23.4%) were attended secondary school and 34(10%) were higher institution. Regarding marital status, 221(66.4%) of the respondents were married. The majority (36.93%) have monthly income of less than 500 ETB (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents in Duber town, Feb, 2016.

Socio-demographic characteristics		Frequency	Percentage	
Sex	Male	183	54.95	
	Female	150	45.05	
Age	15-19	23	6.9	
	20-24	46	13.8	
	25-29	47	14.1	
	30-34	52	15.6	
	35-39	52	15.6	
	40-44	60	18	
	45-49	36	10.8	
	>50	17	5.2	
Marital status	Married	221	66.4	
	Unmarried	62	18.6	
	Divorced	29	8.7	
	Widowed	21	6.3	
Educational status	Illiterate	130	39	
	Informal education	0	0	
	Primary	91	27.3	
	Secondary	78	23.4	
College/ University	College/ University	34	10.2	
	Monthly income (in ETB)	<500	123	36.93
	500-1000	115	34.53	
>1000	95	28.54		

(Source: Ethiopian demographic Health Survey, 2014).

From the total 333 respondents interviewed, 120 (36%) had reported different symptoms of illness for which they were taken different measurements in the last one month before the study period.

Of those who had reported symptoms of illnesses (120), 63(52.5%) treated at health institution, 45 (37.5) were self-medicated whereas 12(10%) did not take any action (the symptoms resolved itself) (Figure 1). From those who practiced self-medication, 24(53.3%) were females and 21(46.7%) were males.

Figure 1: Measure taken against health problems in the last one month by sick individuals in Duber town, Feb.09-20, 2016.

In this study, the most common types of ailments for which the respondents reported to have practiced self-medication were headache 22(30.6%), followed by cough and cold 12(16.7%), fever 9(12.5%) (Table 2).

Table 2: Frequency of reported symptoms of illness, Duber town, Feb.09-20, 2016.

Illness(es)	Frequency	Percentage
Headache	22	30.6
Cough and cold	12	16.7
Fever	9	12.5
Abdominal pain	8	11.1
Eye disease	6	8.4
Toothache	5	6.9
Gastritis	5	6.9
Diarrhea	5	6.9
Total	72	100

The reasons given for self-medication shown in Figure 2. Previous experience (43.6%) and Cost of modern health care (20%) were found the two major reasons given by the respondents for self-medication in this study.

Figure 2: Reason for preferring self-medication by sick persons in Duber town, Feb.09-20, 2016.

Majority of the respondents 24(40.7%) who practiced self-medication were obtained information on self-medication from family members (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Source of information for self-medication for sick persons in Duber town.

The most frequently class of drugs for self-medication were analgesics/antipyretics and antimicrobial which account 24(38.1%) each followed by anti-helminthes 6(9.5%) (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Category of medicinal agents used for self-medication by sick individuals in Duber town, Feb.09/2016-20/2016.

Kiosk was the main source of drugs used for self-medication (Table 3).

Table 3: Source of modern medicine of Duber town community, Duber town, Feb.09/2016-20/2016.

Source of modern medicine for SM	Frequency	Percentage
Kiosk	18	35.3
Private clinic	13	25.5
Drug retail outlet	5	9.8
Neighbor/relatives	5	9.8
Leftover	5	9.8
Homemade remedies	5	9.8
Total	51	100

From the total 333 respondents interviewed 57(17.1%) were practiced drug storing in the house. From this, 25 (36.8%) were store drug to use for emergency cases, 23(33.8%) were to treat similar illness whereas 20(29.4%) were store leftover drug from previous prescription (Table 4).

Table 4: Reason of storing drugs in Duber town community, Duber town, Feb.09-20, 2016.

Reason of storing drugs	Frequency	percentage
For emergency	25	36.8
To treat similar ailments	23	33.8
Leftover from past prescription	20	29.4
Total	68	100

Figure5 shown the types of medicines stored in the house. The most commonly stored drugs are analgesics/antipyretics 32(47.06%) followed by antimicrobial 30(44.12%).

Figure 5: Category of medicine stored in house among Duber town community, Feb.09-20, 2016.

The most common place where a drug stored was locked cabinet (39.70%) followed by open shelf which accounts 38.24 % (figure 6).

Figure 6: Place of household drug storage in Duber town, Feb.09-20, 2016.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the prevalence of self-medication among respondents was found 37.5%. This seems to be less prevalent as compared to the studies done in Kolladiba town, North West Ethiopia [9] and Assendabo town, Jimma zone, southwestern Ethiopia [10]. The lower value in this study could be due to majority of the community access to modern health institutions (both private and government). Even if there was no statistically significant association between sex of respondents and self-medication ($p = 0.230$), the practice of self-medication is higher among females 24(53.3%) as compared to males 21 (46.7%).

The commonest illnesses that led to self-medication in this study were headache, fever, and cough. These were also reported similarly in study conducted in Jimma, Mekelle and Assendabo towns [10,11] The studies done in South India and kolladiba town also pointed out fever, headache and cough and cold as the main ailment that necessitated self-medication intervention [6,9].

The results of a similar study in Mekelle, showed that, people used self-medication mainly because of they have had prior experience to the illness and/or the drug [11]. In contrary to this, the results of studies done in Kolladiba and Assendabo towns revealed that the most common reasons for the practice of self-medication was its relative less cost [9]. Less cost of self-medication was the second main reason for the practice of self-medication. As WHO noted, self-medication provides a cheap alternative to people who cannot afford to pay medical practitioners. Thus, self-medication is often the first response to illness among people with low income [10].

In this study, the three most usual sources of information for self-medication were family members, self-experience and neighbor. According to, study done in Mekelle (by Eticha T, Mesfin K.), pharmacists, healthcare providers such as doctors, nurses and health assistants served as sources of information for self-medication [11]. This difference could be due to lack of health professionals such doctors and pharmacist in this study community. The category of drugs mostly used by the Duber town residents were included analgesics/antipyretics, antimicrobial and anti-helminthes. These findings in agreement with other local study done in kolladiba town [9]. Similarly analgesics were the drugs used for self-medication in study conducted South-east Islamic Republic of Iran [8]. This might be because of such drugs applied to treat uncomplicated common illness such as headache, fever and pain. Antibiotics drugs were found to be self-medicated in the current study. Self-medication with antibiotics can lead to the emergence of the dangerous worldwide problem of antibiotics drug resistant micro-organisms so antibiotic self-medication needs a special attention.

The availability of drugs at shops(kiosk) was also identified in this study which is also source of drugs in study done in Jimma[12]. Private clinics were also identified as the second main sources of modern pharmaceuticals for rampant practice of self-medication which is similar to the study done in Assendabo town [10]. In study conducted in kolladiba town, drug outlets such as drug vendor and pharmacy were identified as the main source of modern drugs for practice of self-medication in contrary to the current study [9].

In this study, 17.1% of respondents were reported drug storing practice in the house. The main reasons for stored drugs in house were to use during emergency situation and to treat similar ailments. Study conducted in South-east Islamic Republic of Iran revealed that the households kept medicines at home either to use them in the future (relapse or emergency) or to give them to someone else who has similar symptoms [8].

As per this study, common places where medicines stored were locked cabinet and open shelf. According to study conducted in South-east Islamic Republic of Iran, the most common place was the refrigerator. This difference might be due to the community store drugs that do not require refrigerator.

CONCLUSIONS

- The community practiced self-medication.
- Previous experience was found the main reason for self-medication.
- Headache, cough and cold and fever were identified as commonly treated ailments by self-medication.
- Analgesic/antipyretics, antibiotics and anti-helminthes were identified commonly used drugs for self-medication.
- Kiosk and private clinics were identified source of modern medicine for self-medication.
- Community practiced drugs storage in the house and further studies are recommended to uncover the effect of self-medication and drug storage.

Abbreviations

ETB	Ethiopian Birr
FDA	Food and Drug Authority
OTC	Over the counter drug
SM	Self-Medication
WHO	World Health Organization

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

SA initiated the research idea, designed the study, and performed analysis. AT participated in initiation of the research idea, designed the study, performance of analysis and drafted the manuscript.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to Jimma University for funding this study

REFERENCES

1. Pandya R, Jhaveri K, Vyas F, Patel V. Prevalence, pattern and perceptions of self-medication in medical students. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol.* 2013;2(3):275–80.
2. Gupta S, Gupta P. Prevalence of Self medication: A Review. *J Manag Sci Technol.* 2014;2(1):35–40.
3. Darshana B. self-medication profile of dental patients in Tumkur, South India. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2013;5(3):926–31.
4. Sherazi B, Mahmood K, Amin F, Zaka M, Riaz M, Javed A. Prevalence and measure of selfmedication: A review. *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2012;4(3):1774–1778.
5. Abula T, Worku A. Self-medication in three towns of North West Ethiopia. *Ethiop J Health Dev.* 2001;15(1):25–30.
6. E B, K G. Prevalence and Pattern of Self Medication use in coastal regions of South India | *British Journal of Medical Practitioners.* *Br J Med Pract.* 2011;4(3):a428.
7. Sharma R, Verma U, Sharma C, Kapoor B. Self-medication among urban population of Jammu city. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2005;37(1):40–3.
8. B F, R F. Household storage of medicines and self-medication practices in south-east Islamic Republic of Iran. *East Mediterr Health J.* 2014 Sep;20(9):547–53.
9. fantahun molla Kassa SA. Self-medication Practice: the Case of Kolladiba Town, North West Ethiopia. *Int J Pharma Sci Res.* 2014;5(10):670–7.
10. Suleman S, Ketsela A, Mekonnen Z. Assessment of self-medication practices in Assendabo town, Jimma zone, southwestern Ethiopia. *Res Soc Adm Pharm RSAP.* 2009 Mar;5(1):76–81.
11. Eticha T, Mesfin K. Self-medication practices in Mekelle, Ethiopia. *PloS One.* 2014;9(5):e97464.
12. Worku S, G/Mariam A. Practice of Self-medication in Jimma Town. *Ethiop J Health Dev.* 2004 Mar 25;17(2):111–6.

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

